

Microemulsion As Novel Drug Delivery Approach: A Review

Neha Jaiswal^{*1}, Mohd. Faizan², Shivangi Singh³, Aman Kumar Singh⁴

^{1,2,3,4}*Rameshwaram Institute of Technology and Management, Lucknow Uttar Pradesh-227202, India*

Address Of Correspondence:

Neha Jaiswal*

Address: Department Of Pharmaceutics, Rameshwaram Institute of Technology and Management, Lucknow Uttar Pradesh-227202, India

ABSTRACT

Microemulsions are an unusual, stable, thermodynamically impressive systems that include relatively 20–200 nm-size droplets made of oil and water with the help of a suitable surfactant. Based on their structure, emulsions are of two types i.e. o/w (oil in water) and w/o (water-in-oil). These are known as liquid preparation in which the tension between oils and water phase is extremely low. These polymersomes have recently received extensive attention from researchers, owing to their ability to incorporate various medicinal molecules. Such systems will provide stability against oxidation and enzymatic hydrolysis of drug and also improve the solubility of lipophilic drugs ensuring better bioavailability. There are also several ways of administering them, such as through the eyes, mouth, lungs, vagina and skin. They include self-assembly ability, simplicity in production processes and scale-up techniques, thermodynamic stability, increased solubility for lipophilic drugs and improved bioavailability. This paper focuses on the use of microemulsions in topical and other applications with minimal systemic uptake.

Keywords - Microemulsion, Thermodynamically stable, Surfactant, Co-Surfactant, Phase Inversion, Packing Ratio.

Introduction

They can administer drugs directly to the living parts of the skin, bypassing oral or systemic treatments by passing through the horny layer. Changes have occurred in utilization of microemulsion based system in various chemical and industrial processes over the last twenty years. The development in this area has seen their introduction from oil recovery which started in 1970's to pharmaceuticals and cosmetics ten years ago. This is because they offer an alternative delivery vehicle to other systems such as colloidal systems under investigation, traditional emulsions, suspensions, micellar solutions and others (Nayak et al., 2008). For example during dermal administration of drugs, these methods enable prolonged or controlled drug release via percutaneous, peroral ophthalmic and parenteral routes. They also have a number of other advantages such as easy scale up and manufacturing process that can be done spontaneously and thermodynamic stability as well as enhanced solubility of hydrophobic drugs and greater bioavailability than most oral formulations (Nayak et al., 2008). Furthermore, there may be less comedogenicity with respect to creams or solutions when using inverted micellar microemulsions. This can be achieved by the use of appropriate surfactants or a combination thereof, when oil and water are mixed to form a single phase which are normally immiscible. In the case of microemulsion systems, cosurfactants are typically short-to-medium chain alcohols. Surfactant and cosurfactant create an extremely low interfacial tension in the system that triggers spontaneous formation of microemulsions having an average droplet size varying between 10 and 140 nm. In comparison to other conventional carriers Microemulsions have been shown to increase solubility in addition to serving as a better carrier for poorly soluble drugs enabling them deliver poorly soluble drugs.^[2,3]

Advantage of Microemulsion

Microemulsions can serve as medication carriers for multiple routes of delivery. These have advantages over other systems.

- These are stable and need low energy to create.
- Manufacturing and scaling are made easier.
- Improved medication solubility and bioavailability.
- In delivery of poorly soluble drug.

- As a novel drug deliver system.^[8]

Components Of Microemulsion

Several oils and surfactants make up microemulsion systems. Their use is limited due to unknown mechanisms of action, toxicity, and potential for irritation— thus one should select biocompatible, non-toxic materials that are clinically acceptable. It is also important to use emulsifiers within an appropriate concentration range when designing microemulsion systems. The term "microemulsion" was first introduced by Schulman et al. back in 1959; they created stable homogeneous quaternary systems showing opalescence upon dilution with water. This revealed phase behavior where the alcohol droplets formed the moment a short chain alcohol was added to such transparent mixtures— consisting of water plus oil (benzene) and two surfactants as well as a cosurfactant at specific proportions (hexanol, potassium oleate). The coarse emulsion is titrated with clarity by introducing another surface-active ingredient after its formation from components selected according to prescribed rules (Schulman's method). Emulsion transparency leads to optical effect observation described as "interesting". The achievement of system spontaneous clearing is dependent on the appropriate combination of the four components. Schulman's investigation revolved around four-component systems which consisted of hydrocarbons (either aliphatic or aromatic), ionic surfactants, co-surfactants (commonly aliphatic alcohols with 4- to 8-carbon chains) and an aqueous phase. Having extensively worked on monolayers, Schulman was able to utilize his knowledge in this area for the development of microemulsions. When surfactants and co-surfactants are carefully selected to form a mixed film at the oil/water interface, the resultant interfacial pressure is increased further beyond its initial positive tension— a principle introduced by Schulman himself. It was observed by Schulman and his team that addition of a co-surfactant into a coarse microemulsion can result in low viscosity as well as isotropic transparency besides stability after formation. The evolution from an opaque emulsion to a see-through solution takes place effortlessly— and it takes place unmistakably. These systems consist of tiny spherical microdroplets, varying in size from 600 to 8000 nm. It was in 1959 when Schulman first used the term "microemulsions" to refer to these systems; before this, he had used terms like clear water and oil dispersion or oleopathic hydromicelles, oleopathic hydromicelles. Microemulsions find various applications such as oil recovery or production of nanoparticles: topical formulations are designed for targeted delivery to specific body areas with minimal systemic absorption. Conventional delivery involves barrier modulation using antibiotics and antibacterial agents— not aggressively.^[4]

Oil Phase

Curvature is influenced by oil which penetrates and result in swelling of tail region of surfactant. Unlike long chain oil short chain oils are more likely to penetrate the tail region thus leading to greater negative curvature and a lower effective HLB. Both unsaturated fatty acids and saturated fatty acids have their own unique penetration-enhancing properties that have been extensively studied. Lipophilic drugs easily get dissolve in o/w type microemulsions. The oil phase selected is based on drug to be dissolved. This approach reduces formulation volume while providing therapeutic dose levels within an encapsulated form of the drug.^[22]

Surfactants

While preparing microemulsion in order to facilitate the dispersion process, the selected surfactant should lower the tension between layers of oil and water to a very small value. It must should be able to lower interfacial tension and provide a flexible film that can readily deform around the droplets. It is widely acknowledged that surfactants with low HLB (<12)

are more suited for creating w/o microemulsions, whereas those with high HLB (>12) are better suited for creating o/w microemulsions. Cosurfactants are frequently needed to lower the effective HLB of surfactants with HLB values higher than 20 to a range where microemulsion production is possible.^[5]

Co-surfactants

In general surfactant are able to form a stable emulsion but Co-surfactants enable the interfacial film to have the required flexibility that allows it accommodate different curvatures, hence leading to formation of microemulsions over a wide composition range (7, 12, and 14). If an ideal single surfactant membrane is to be formed, then lipophilic chains should be suitably short or have fluidizing elements like unsaturated bonds. For reducing interfacial tension more, short- or medium- chain alcohols can serve as co-surfactants.^[36]

Structure

Dynamic systems, microemulsions, have interfaces that fluctuate naturally and continuously. They come in three different structural categories: bicontinuous microemulsions, w/o (water-in-oil), and o/w (oil-in-water). In w/o microemulsions, water droplets are dispersed within the continuous oil phase while oil droplets are dispersed in the continuous aqueous phase for oil-in-water microemulsions. In such a situation where there is similar content of water and oil, a bicontinuous microemulsion can form. The interface is stabilized in all these forms of emulsion by help of surfactant and co-surfactant. When constituents' proportions vary, one can obtain a mixture of surfactants, water and oil with various structures and phases.^[6,37]

Fig no.:1 Structure of Microemulsion

Classification

According to Winsor there are four type of phases of micro-emulsion can exist in equilibrium; known as Winsor phases. They are as follows:

- Winsor I: This is also known as two-phase system with upper oil layer
- Winsor II: This is also known as two-phase system with lower water layer.
- Winsor III: This is a three-phase system.
- Winsor IV: This is a single-phase system

Fig no.:2 Winsor phases I, II, III and IV are shown schematically (how the phases change)

The R-ratio is one of the characterization concepts introduced by Winsor and its purpose is to describe how solvents and amphiphiles affect interfacial curvature. It relates the amphiphile's propensity to disperse in oil to its water solubility. When one phase is preferred over the other, there is a distinct curvature of the interface region. Thus, when $R > 1$, contact area with oil increases while contact area with water decreases. This therefore implies that oil becomes the formatting and continuous phase in microemulsion.^[7]

Steps involved in microemulsion

Preparing water phase

- Component soluble in water are first dissolved in water.
- Heating may be required.
- Centrifugation may be required to remove undissolved particle.

Preparing oil phase

- Component soluble in oil are dissolved in oil phase.

Emulsifying water and oil phase

- Suitable container is used for mixing.
- Emulsion is formed by using suitable technique.^[9]

Method For Preparation Of Microemulsion

Phase titration method

Phase diagrams clear illustrations of microemulsions obtained from the phase titration method. Decoupage of phase diagrams in another important tool to study these complex interactions which happen when several substances are taken in combination. When two components come together with a defined chemical structure and concentration; several association structures are generated including, emulsions, micelles, lamellar or hexagonal gels among others besides oily dispersion as well as microemulsions. In this research,

determination of phase boundaries and understanding of their phase equilibria in a broader sense is the main objective.^[14]

For showing different zones Pseudo-ternary phase diagram based on 100% of specific component each corner of the diagram is generally used [17]. On the other hand, quaternary phase diagrams (four-component systems), are difficult to draw and hard to understand. This region can be identified for their classification as w/o or o/w microemulsion but based on temperature composition whether water rich and oil-rich phase. it's advisable to be careful with observations so to not bring up any information about metastable systems and such.^[10,11]

Fig no.:3 Hypothetical phase regions of microemulsion system

Phase inversion method

A microemulsions Phase inversion occurs when there is excessive dispersed phase or fluctuations in temperature. This unfailingly results in pronounced physicochemical modifications, including variable particle sizes and could exert a profound effect on in vitro as well as “in vivo profile” drug release. These methods work by influencing the surfactant’s degree of spontaneous curvature. In the specific case of non-ionic surfactants, the transition can be reached by cooling to a temperature where an o/w microemulsion becomes finely dispersed oil droplets at around their point off zero spontaneous curvature and surface tension minimum. The technique described above is known as the PIT (Phase Inversion Temperature) approach.

Additionally, other alternatives to the temperature like pH level or salt concentration can be taken into account. Water droplets are initially generated when the water was titrated slowly into oil. As the water volume percentage is increased, the spontaneous curvature of surfactant

changes from that of stabilising a w/o microemulsion to o/w at locus of inversion. Moreover, by adjusting the temperature of the system it is possible to obtain a emulsion at higher temperatures which is of w/o type microemulsion. ^[39,40]

Evaluation of microemulsion

The following methods are used to assess the microemulsions. They are as follows:

Phase behaviour studies

For differentiating microemulsion from other system, three methods may be employed:

1. Phase contrast microscopy
2. Freeze fracture transmission electron microscopy
3. Visual inspections

Microemulsions are defined as clear, isotropic one-phase systems; on the other hand, liquid crystalline systems would appear opaque and exhibit birefringence when observed under cross-polarized light microscopy. ^[12]

Scattering techniques

Different scattering techniques like light, small angle X-ray, and neutron scattering were utilized for study of microemulsion structure. These techniques are particularly valuable when examining dilute monodisperse spheres commonly encountered in microemulsions. ^[15]

Rheology

The identification of the microemulsion from other similar system like liquid crystals is aided by changes in the rheological properties. Dynamic formations known as bicontinuous microemulsions exhibit constant changes among the swelling reverse micelle, swollen micelles, and bicontinuous structure. ^[18]

Viscosity measurement

For the measurement of viscosity of microemulsion a Brookfield viscometer can be used. The viscosity of microemulsions is tested at different temperatures. To ensure accurate measurements, keep the instrument at $37 \pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$ and submerge the samples before testing. ^[13]

Interfacial tension

To study the formation of these microemulsions and to analyse their properties, the interfacial tension has to be measured since low ultra-values of interfacial tension are related to the phase behaviour of a system indicating the presence of the surfactant with the aqueous and oil phases. To measure ultra-low Interfacial Tension, a spinning-drop is used. The principle is based on the measurement of the shape of a low-density drop rotating in a cylindrical capillary filled with a high-density phase. ^[16]

Droplet size

Measuring the size distribution of droplets in microemulsions is done by light scattering or electron microscopy. With this method, one can easily tell how stable a micro emulsion will be.

- Dynamic Light Scattering measurements
- Polydispersity

- Phase Analysis^[17,34]

Factors affecting Microemulsion

Packing ratio

The HLB of a surfactant impacts molecular arrangement and film curvature, thus defining the kind of microemulsion formed. Examining film curvature can show surfactant association, which is crucial for microemulsion production.^[21]

Properties of surfactants, oil phases, and temperature

It depends on surfactant that which type of microemulsion is formed employed since these substances have both water-friendly and oil-friendly ends. In every surfactant's HLB value within any given system, the balance between its affinity for water (hydrophilic) and that for oil (lipophilic) is determined by how the head group interacts with water and how the tail group interacts with oil. High concentrations of surfactant or the presence of salt may lead to decreased dissociation of polar groups hence creating a w/o system. Lowering the polar group association energy by adding water would result in an o/w system with increased dissociation rate due to dilution method. Temperature greatly affects ionic surfactant properties through charge modification which is brought about by surfactant counterion dissociation enhancement. The oil component changes the curvature of membranes by inserting itself into the monolayer tail group region where it causes swelling; this is because different oils can be used. Short chain oils penetrate much more deeply into the lipophilic group region than long chain ones thereby giving rise to higher negative curvatures.

They are hydrophilic at low temperatures and generally are oil in water emulsifiers. They become lipophilic at high temperatures and tend to be water in oil emulsifiers. When excess water and oil are mixed with microemulsions at moderate temperatures, then they form bicontinuous structures.^[38]

The chain length, kind, and nature of cosurfactants

The most often used cosurfactants in microemulsions is alcohol. Cosurfactants with shorter chains have a positively curved effect because the head area is swelling to a greater degree than the tail end is, which makes them more hydrophilic and therefore favours o/w type. On the other hand, cosurfactants with longer chains tend to favour w/o type by swelling more around their chain regions than near their head groups.^[23]

Temperature

Temperature is important for determining the size of active head groups in nonionic surfactants. These surfactants form oil-in-water structures at lower temperatures because they are hydrophilic while water-in-oil structures form at higher temperatures owing to their lipophilic nature. When a microemulsion coexists with excess oil and water phases, a bicontinuous system is formed at an intermediate temperature.^[29]

Applications

Application in Oral drug delivery

The ability of microemulsion water solubilize, clinical potency, increase bioavailability and minimize drug side-effects, makes them be preferred over conventional oral formulations for oral delivery (Charman 2000). These are capable of carrying hormones, steroids, antibiotics

as well as diuretics among other drugs. Oral route is the most common way through which drugs are administered in various disease states. However, oral administration of oil soluble drugs presents a challenge due to their poor aqueous solubility. One approach used to address this issue is by delivering such compounds in microemulsified form. Scientists have faced difficulties in developing an appropriate system for oral drug delivery because these agents tend to precipitate or decompose in gastrointestinal fluids.^[19]

Application in Parenteral drug delivery

Transfer pharmaceuticals with limited solubility by injection, especially the intravenous route is a big problem in the industry because little of the drug gets to where it is needed. On the other hand, fine droplet microemulsions show longer residence time in the body than coarse ones when given through a parenteral route due to slow clearance rate of the former.^[32]

The use of both o/w and w/o microemulsions has been made in intravenous administration. Despite the several microemulsion systems reported in the literature, only a small number are suitable for parenteral administration because of surfactant toxicity.^[24,25]

Application in Topical drug delivery

Administration of topical drugs has a number of benefits over other methods which include bypassing hepatic first pass metabolism with its associated toxicities, as well as enabling direct delivery and localization of therapy on the diseased skin or eyes. For prostaglandin E1 study on hairless mouse model, O/W and W/O microemulsions were assessed.^[20]

The o/w microemulsion exhibited greater release rate however less permeation rate which was inadequate for practical purpose. FTIR and DSC showed that IPP organogel after incubating for one day changed lipid structure in the stratum corneum of human skin. Moreover, w/o microemulsion was employed in investigating diphenhydramine hydrochloride which is a hydrophilic drug distribution through the skin of an excised human being.^[27,28]

Application in Ocular and Pulmonary drug delivery

Eye problems are commonly solved by applying drugs on the affected area. In a bid to investigate ways of delivering medications locally into the eye, for drug dissolution, absorption, and long-term release profiles, dual surfactants based oil in water type of microemulsions (O/W) have been formulated. However, for ophthalmic drug delivery systems, lecithin, propylene glycol, and PEG 200 were employed as co-surfactants whereas isopropyl myristate (IPM) served as the oil phase for preparation of Pilocarpine microemulsions. Because they had low viscosity and refractive index which are desirable properties in this formulations, they were found suitable for ocular drug delivery systems. Moreover, a water-in-hexafluoride propellant microemulsion using non-ionic fluorinated surfactants for pulmonary administration was also reported.^[33,35]

Application in Biotechnology

This in fact is a prevalent situation in the cases of enzymatic and bio-catalytic reactions, which most commonly occur in pure or aquea-organic media, and utilize biphasic media. Apolar, pure medium can denature biocatalysts. The use of water-poor media provides some advantages. As has been partially mentioned above, enzymes with water content of less than 50 per cent show the following properties:

- Enhanced solubility in nonpolar reactants
- Possible shift in thermodynamic equilibrium in favour of condensations.

- Improved heat stability of enzymes allows for higher temperature reactions.^[30,31]

Other applications

- Microemulsions have been found to enhance the skin penetration of lycopene
- Utilized for the transdermal penetration of drugs such as Nimesulide.
- Microemulsion applications include oil recovery, detergent, cosmetics, agrochemicals, and food.
- They are also employed for environmental cleanup and detoxification.
- Microemulsions are used as fuel, lubricants, cutting oils, corrosion inhibitors, coatings, and textile finishing.
- The synthesis of microemulsions in a microporous medium using the gel method has also been explored, and microemulsions are utilized in analytical applications.
- Novel liquid/membranes such as microemulsions and crystalline colloidal arrays are being investigated for chemical sensors.^[41]

Conclusion

It is still early to fully realize the promise of microemulsion technologies, and it is anticipated that the field of microemulsion technology would see several advancements. Microemulsion systems play a critical role in offering innovative approaches to address the issue of poor aqueous solubility of highly lipophilic medicinal compounds and in achieving high, more reliable, and repeatable bioavailability. The ease with which formulations can be scaled up is crucial from an industrial perspective, given the relative expense of commercial manufacturing. Many topical products using the microemulsion technique are expected to emerge, in addition to oral drug delivery, which is important from the perspective of both the enormous and profitable cosmetic industry prospects as well as the delivery of drugs. The creation of safer, more effective, and more compatible microemulsion ingredients is the focus of current research efforts, which will increase the usefulness of these innovative vehicles. Despite the challenges associated with this therapeutic system, there seems to be a current research focus on realizing its full potential as a revolutionary drug delivery technique.

REFERENCES

1. Acharya, S. P., Moulik, S. K. Sanyal, Mishra, B. K. And Puri, P. M. Physicochemical Investigations of Microemulsification of Coconut Oil and Water Using Polyoxyethylene 2-Cetyl Ether (Brij 52) and Isopropanol or Ethanol, *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science* 2002, 245:163–170.
2. Agrawal OP, Agrawal S. An overview of new drug Delivery system: microemulsion. *Asian J Pharm Sci Tech.*, 2012; 2(5): 1-8.
3. Agarwal P, Semimul A. A comprehensive Review on sustained release matrix tablets: a Promising dosage form. *Universal Journal of Pharmaceutical Research* 2018; 3(6): 49-54.
4. Algin Yapar E, Beskan U, Karavana SY. A Recent overview of locally administered topical Otic dosage forms. *Universal Journal of Pharmaceutical Research* 2019; 4(4): 39-42
5. Anayatollah S, Moghimipour E and Leis F. Preparation and Evaluation of TretinoinMicroemulsion Based on Pseudo Ternary Phase Diagrams. *Advanced Pharmaceutical Bulletin*.2 (2); 2012: 141-147
6. Attwood D., Mallon C., Taylor CJ., Phase studies of oil in water phospholipid microemulsion, *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*, 1992, 84: R5-R8.

7. Bagley DM, Gardner JR, Holland G, Lewis RW, Regnier JF, Stringer DA, et al. Skin irritation: Reference chemicals data bank. *Toxicol In Vitro*. 1996;10:1–6.
8. Bellare JR, Haridas MM, Li XJ. Characterization of microemulsions using fast freeze fracture and cry-electron microscopy. In Kumar P, Mittal KL. (ed.) *Handbook of microemulsion science and technology*. Marcel Dekker, New York, 1999, 411–35.
9. Dreher F, Walde P, Luisi PL, Elsner P. Human skin irritation studies of a lecithin microemulsion gel and of lecithin liposomes. *Skin Pharmacol*. 1996;9:124–9.
10. Gadhawe A. D, Waghmare J.T, A Short Review on Microemulsion And Its Application in Extraction of Vegetable Oil, *International Journal of Research In Engineering And Technology*, 2321-7308.
11. Ghosh, S.; Johns, R. T. Dimensionless Equation of State to Predict Microemulsion Phase Behavior. *Langmuir* 2016, 32 (35), 8969, DOI: 10.1021/acs.langmuir.6b02666
12. Gogarty, W. B. And Olson, R. W., “Use of Microemulsions in Miscible-Type Oil Recovery Procedure,”U.S. Patent No. 3,254,714 (1962).60. Danielson, H. H., Paynter, W. T. And Milton, H. W
13. Jogani VV, Shah PJ, Mishra P, Mishra AK, Misra A(2008) Intranasal mucoadhesive Micro-emulsion of tacrine to improve brain Targeting. *Alzheimer Disease and Associated Disorders* , 116-124 Maher A, Ibrahim K, Mohammad AH. Topical Salicylic acid and Lactic acid microemulsion. *Org Med Chem Int J.*, 2017; 2(3): 1-4.
14. Ktistis, G., Niopas, I., 1998: A study on the in-vitro percutaneous absorption of propranolol from disperse systems. *J. Pharm.Pharmacol*. 50, 413–418.
15. Khorsandi, S.; Qiao, C.; Johns, R. T.; Torrealba, V. A. In *Simulation of Surfactant-Polymer Floods with a Novel Microemulsion Equation of State* , SPE – DOE Improved Oil Recovery Symposium Proceedings, 2016.
16. Kumar. K. Senthil et al. Microemulsions as carrier for Novel Drug Delivery: A Review. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical sciences Review and Research* 2011; 10: 37-45.
17. Khan AY, Talegaonkar S, Iqbal Z, Ahmed FJ, Khar RK. Multiple emulsions: an overview. *Current Drug Delivery*.3(4), 2006, 429-43.
18. Kumar P, Mittal KL. *Handbook of Micro emulsion Science And Technology*; 1st Edition; CRC Press, New York, 1999
19. Lawrence M J & Rees G D. (2000). Microemulsion Based media as novel drug delivery systems. *Advanced Drug Delivery Reviews*. 45(1), 89-121. DOI: 10.1016/S0169-409X(00)00103-4.
20. Lawrence M J. (1994). Surfactant systems: Microemulsions and vesicles as vehicles for drug Delivery. *European Journal of Drug Metabolism and Pharmacokinetics*. 19(3), 257-269. DOI: 10.1007/BF03188929.
21. Lawrence M, Gareth D. Microemulsion-based media as novel drug delivery systems. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev*. 2000;45:89–121
22. Lessner E, Kahlweit M & Strey R. (1983). Influence Of the properties of the oil and the surfactant on the Phase behavior of systems of the type H₂O-oil-nonionic surfactant. *Journal of Physical Chemistry*.87, 5032-5040. DOI: 10.1021/j150642a051.
23. Lopez F, Cinelli G, Ambrosone L, Colafemmina G, Ceglie A & Palazzo G. (2004). Role of the Cosurfactant in water-in-oil microemulsion: Interfacial properties tune the enzymatic activity of Lipase. *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical And Engineering Aspects*. 237(1-3), 49-59.DOI:10.1016/j.colsurfa.2004.01.027
24. Patel MR, Patel RB, Parikh JR, Solanki AB, Patel BG. Effect of formulation components on the in vitro permeation of microemulsion drug delivery system of fluconazole. *AAPS PharmSci Tech*. 2009;10:917–23.
25. Patel V, Kukadiya H, Mashru R, Surti N, Mandal S. Development of microemulsion for solubility enhancement of clopidogrel. *Iran J Pharm Res*. 2010;9:327–34.

26. Prajapati SK, Kumar S, Singh A, Singh A. Development and characterization of topical Microemulsion of Levofloxacin. *World J Pharm Pharm Sci.*, 2013; 2(6): 5935-47.
27. Paul B K & Moulik S P. (2001). Uses and Applications of microemulsions. *Current Science.* 80(8), 990-1001.
28. Pedersen J S. (1999). Analysis of small-angle Scattering data from micelles and microemulsions: Free-form approaches and model fitting. *Current Opinion in Colloid and Interface Science.* 4(3), 190-196. DOI: 10.1016/S1359-0294(99)00033-3.
29. Piorkowski D T & McClements D J. (2013). Beverage emulsions: Recent developments in Formulation, production and applications. *Food Hydrocolloids.*
30. Podlogar F, Gasperlin M, Tomsic M, Jamnik A & Bester Rogac M. (2004). Structural characterisation Of water-Tween 40®/Inwitor 308®- Isopropylmyristate microemulsions usinf different Experimental methods. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics.* 276(1-2), 115-128. DOI: 10.1016/S0168-3659(02)00049-4.
31. Porras M, Solans C, Gonzalez, C, Martinez A, Guinart A & Gutierrez, J M. (2004). Studies of Formation of w/o nanoemulsions. *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects.* 249(1-3), 115-118. DOI: 10.1016/j.colsurfa.2004.05.025.
32. Radi M, Abbasi S, Hamidi Z & Azizi M –H. (2013). Development of a new method for extraction of Conola oil using lecithin based microemulsion Systems. *Food Technology.* 24(5). 70-72
33. Sarkar B, Hardenia S. Microemulsion drug delivery system: For oral bioavailability enhancement of glipizide. *J Adv Pharm Educ Res.* 2011;1:195–200.
34. Shrestha S, Pokhrel S, Sharma S, Manandhar M, Alam I. Formulation and evaluation of topical Microemulgel loaded with Terbinafine Hcl Microemulsion. *Int J Pharm Sci Res.,* 2017; 8(11):4716-23.
35. Shah P, Swarnkar D. Development and characterization of microemulsion containing antihypertensive agent using factorial design. *J Pharm Bioallied Sci.* 2012;4:69–70.
36. Singh V, Bushettii SS, Raju AS, Ahmad R, Singh M, Bisht A. Microemulsions as promising delivery systems: A Review. *Indian J Pharm Educ Res.* 2011;45:392–401.
37. Suppaibulsuk B, Prasassarakich P, Rempel GL. Factorial design for nanosized polyisoprene synthesis via differential microemulsion polymerization. *Polym Adv Technol.* 2010;21:467–75.
38. Tagavifar, M.; Herath, S.; Weerasooriya, U. P.; Sepehrnoori, K.; Pope, G. Measurement of Microemulsion Viscosity and Its Implications for Chemical Enhanced Oil Recovery. *SPE J.* 2018, 23, 66– 83, DOI: 10.2118/179672-PA
39. Tang JL, Sun J, He ZG. Self-Emulsifying Drug Delivery Systems: Strategy for Improving Oral Delivery of Poorly Soluble Drugs. *Current Drug Therapy.* 2(1), 2007, 85-93.
40. Talegaonkar S, Azeem A, Ahmad FJ, Khar RK, Pathan SA, Khan ZI. Micro emulsions: A Novel Approach to Enhanced Drug Delivery. *Recent Patents on Drug Delivery & Formulation.* 2(3), 2008, 238-257.
41. Zhua W, Guo C. Microemulsion-based hydrogel formulation of pencyclovir for topical delivery. *Int J Pharm.* 2009;378:152–8.